

Water Quality of the Brahmani River Upstream and Downstream at Effluent Discharge Point of Talcher Industrial Complex of Orissa

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Water samples collected from the river Brahmani upstream, downstream of effluent discharge point of Talcher industrial complex and effluent of the said complex from the Nandira jhor have been analysed. It has been observed that some parameters of these water samples are within the tolerance limit as specified by WHO and ISI, but many other parameters are beyond the said limit. It has been concluded that the water of the river Brahmani in this zone is fully contaminated with toxic ingredients and responsible for the health hazards of the inhabitants of this region.

In India, many cities and industrial complexes have come up on the bank of rivers in order to meet the increasing demand of water for various purpose. But on the otherhand, these rivers are used as the sink of all types of wastes which pollutes these essential sources of water. The river Brahmani is one of the fourteen major river systems in India having catchment area more than 20000 sq. km. Only four out of these fourteen river systems are perennial and the Brahmani system is one of them. The upper reaches of the Brahmani is known as the South Koel which has only one important tributary, the Sankha. The river has been named Brahmani from the place Vedavyas which happens to be the meeting spot of the Sankha, is nearer to Rourkela steel city. It is the second longest river of Orissa covering a distance of 430 km with a drainage area of 7240 sq. km. It passes through four major districts, namely, Sundergarh, Sambalpur, Dhenkanal and Cuttack; and ultimately meets the Bay of Bengal at Dhamara. From the origin to the point of emergence of distributaries in the coastal plains its water is classified under class 'C'. It means water is suitable for drinking with conventional treatment followed by disinfection, which is not so at present.

Two major industrial complexes are situated on the bank of the river Brahmani at Rourkela and Talcher. Rourkela industrial complex is very close and Talcher complex is about 8-10 km away from the river bank. The effect of effluent of Rourkela complex on the water of this river has been studied by us¹. The present work deals with the assessment of water quality of the river Brahmani polluted by the waste effluent of Talcher industrial complex drained through the Nandira jhor into the river. This complex grew up nearby the coal mines of Talcher. It consists of thermal power station, coal-based fertiliser plant of FCI producing urea, heavy

water plant and Orissa Chemical Limited. The effluent of the fertiliser plant is drained through the Deogharan Nalah which finally meets the Nandira jhor carrying effluents of other units and waste water of Talcher township. The total waste borne by the Nandira jhor finally enters into the river Brahmani just after the pump house of NALCO from where water is being collected for NALCO township.

The samples for the present studies were collected and analysed from three stations as mentioned below (Fig. 1). (I) Talcher (Upstream, US): This spot is about 7 km away from and to the north of Talcher town and 2 km up to NALCO pump house. (II) Nandira (Effluent, EF): This spot is the meeting place of the Nandira jhor with the mainstream of the river Brahmani. (III) Kamalanga (Downstream, DS): It is the next sampling station about 4 km down of Nandira.

Fig. 1

Experimental

Water samples were collected from the monitoring stations (I), (II) and (III) for 2 years (1986–87) at monthly interval, and specifically for station (II) daily collection was done for eight months (May–December, 1987). Generally samples were collected during daytime from 10 a.m. to 3 p.m. at a distance of about 5 m inside the river from the bank and at a depth of about 0.25 m.

The water samples were characterised in terms of parameters like temperature, pH, conductivity, dissolved oxygen, COD, BOD, dissolved CO₂, total alkalinity, total hardness, total solids, dissolved solids, suspended solids and chloride, along with presence of metallic radicals and organic substances. Dissolved oxygen, temperature and pH of the samples were recorded on the spot. Water for dissolved oxygen determination was collected in BOD bottles. The samples were then carried to the laboratory and analysed by standard methods².

Results and Discussion

The physicochemical parameters of the water samples of the river Brahmani at Talcher (US), Kamalanga (DS) and of the effluent of Talcher industrial complex just before entering into the river at Nandira (EF) are presented in Table 1, where seasonal variations are also shown. The following observations have been made.

The temperatures of the water of Nandira and downstream are higher in comparison to that of upstream water in all the seasons. The slight increase in temperature of EF and DS may be due to the effluents emerging out of different industries. Rise in temperature of water source reduces its dissolved oxygen content (DO) and it causes harm to aquatic life.

From the pH value it is evident that the water of US, EF and DS are alkaline in nature. The

effluent water is more alkaline during all seasons. This may be due to the ash and ammoniacal liquor coming in the effluent from the industrial complex. The alkalinity is less during the rainy season, may be due to dilution. During all the seasons the lower limit of dissolved oxygen in DS is much less in comparison to US and EF. This parameter is also much less in effluent during winter. Clean surface water is normally saturated with 7.6 mg dm⁻³ of DO at 30°. DO determines the water quality for various purpose and it depends on the physical, chemical and biological activities of the water body. The drop of lower limit of DO in DS may be due to the effect of mixing of the effluent with the downstream water and it brings about various changes in the water body as mentioned earlier.

The high conductivity values of water of EF and DS in comparison to US during all seasons indicate that considerable amount of ionic substances are present in the industrial waste carried by the Nandira jhor. During rainy season the upper limit of conductivity values are high at all the sampling stations. This may be due to the dissolved minerals washed away from the landscape and agricultural fields by rain water into the river.

High COD and BOD in the source of water cause oxygen depletion to the level detrimental to the aquatic life. In the present study the upper limit of COD at all sampling stations throughout the year is quite high and much above the tolerance limit³, i.e. 10 mg dm⁻³. The BOD values are also considerably high and above the tolerance limit⁴, i.e. 3 mg dm⁻³.

The dissolved CO₂ amount is high in EF throughout the year whereas during rain and winter it is more in DS than US. It has been observed that the total alkalinity of EF and DS are very high in comparison to that of US. The total alkalinity desirable⁵ in the water meant for domestic supply should be 100 mg dm⁻³. However, high alkalinity of water is not harmful to living beings.

TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL DATA OF WATER SAMPLES OF DIFFERENT LOCATION IN DIFFERENT SEASONS*

Parameters**	Talcher (Upstream)			Effluent Nandira jhor			Kamalanga (Downstream)		
	Summer	Rainy	Winter	Summer	Rainy	Winter	Summer	Rainy	Winter
Temp. (°C)	27–31	25–31	22–27	28–31	27–31	25–28	27–31	26–31	25–28
pH	7.5–9.0	7.5–8.7	6.9–7.6	8.0–8.9	7.9–9.2	8.0–8.1	7.9–8.9	7.5–8.6	7.2–7.8
Conductivity (mmho cm ⁻¹)	0.1–0.18	0.18–0.55	0.1–0.25	0.18–0.26	0.14–0.81	0.15–0.6	0.18–0.35	0.14–0.80	0.11–0.52
COD	3.9–28.8	4.3–30.24	4.9–72.0	14.57–24.8	8.6–99.3	4.3–72.0	6.0–24.8	4.3–43.2	4.0–200
BOD	5.2–6.0	6.0–7.0	5.2–6.8	4.6–6.1	6.2–7.0	5.6–6.2	0.6–3.2	4.0–6.2	0.6–4.6
Dissolved CO ₂	3.5–9.2	1.32–12.82	6.9–17.6	1.76–11.78	1.76–23.7	3.5–21.12	2.46–9.21	1.58–18.0	3.0–19.36
Total alkalinity	58–80	13–110	48–91	61–140	30–245	54–190	85–110	13–181	54–200
Total hardness	38–105	24–152	42–115	30–270	30–168	40–800	30–210	24–148	40–250
Chloride	7.7–89	7.8–102	9.4–109	17.5–108.4	8.4–262.7	16.8–126.4	24.55–94.6	7.0–227.9	10–142
Total solid (g dm ⁻³)	0.826–1.8	1.25–2.5	1.3–2.0	1.65–3.5	1.25–3.55	1.62–3.1	1.52–2.5	1.52–2.87	1.62–2.81
Total suspended solid	40–350	400–1086	50–726	300–1432	450–2634	300–1999	250–944	450–1212	300–1696
Dissolved solid (g dm ⁻³)	0.612–1.75	0.831–2.1	1.25–1.5	1.25–3.1	0.6–0.922	1.22–2.8	0.6–2.1	0.92–1.742	1.118–1.12
Dissolved O ₂	6.0–10.6	8.5–14.2	7.0–12.7	4.9–8.1	1.8–9.5	2.0–7.8	4.9–7.1	1.9–11.2	1.8–8.4

*Samples collected during 1986–87; in Orissa broadly March–June is summer, July–October rainy and November–February is winter.

**Unit in (mg dm⁻³) wherever unit is not mentioned (except pH).

The discharged effluent is responsible for the high alkalinity of the DS at Kamalanga. Total hardness of the EF and DS during summer and winter are beyond the permissible limit, i.e. 200 mg dm⁻³; this parameter of US is within the limit during the year. However the World Health Organisation⁵ recommends 500 mg dm⁻³ of hardness in terms of CaCO₃ as permissible limit. Higher concentration of chloride gives an undesirable taste to water. Lockhart *et al.*⁶ reported that the taste thresholds for chloride ion in water varied from 210 to 300 mg dm⁻³; the prescribed limit of WHO⁵ for being 250 mg dm⁻³. The tolerance limit⁴ of chloride in class 'C' water and water meant for irrigation is 600 mg dm⁻³. Hence the water of this zone of the river Brahmani is suitable for domestic and irrigation purpose so far as the concentration of chloride ion is concerned.

The amount of dissolved solids in the effluent water is very high during summer and winter seasons. Though these values are lower in US and DS water in comparison to EF, the water of this zone is not suitable for domestic use and irrigation throughout the year. The recommended tolerance limit⁴ of dissolved solids for class 'C' water and water meant for irrigation are 1500 and 2100 mg dm⁻³ respectively. The total suspended solids in EF and DS are higher than US during all seasons. The water of the Nandira jhor contains ash, coal dust and other impurities to such an extent that the downstream of the river looks brownish black during winter and summer seasons. The people of nearby villages of this zone of the river are using the river water for domestic purpose with much hesitation due to its repelling colour, odour and taste during the dry seasons in absence of other alternative source of water.

The water quality of the Nandira jhor alone has been examined daily continuously for a period of eight months. The physicochemical parameters determined have been furnished in Table 2. The pH of water is always in alkaline range and has exceeded the tolerance limit⁴, i.e. 6.5–8.5 prescribed for class 'C' water. However, this pH is not harmful for fish culture and irrigation. The dissolved oxygen content of this water is also high. The approved

limits of dissolved oxygen for class 'C' water and water for fish culture are 4 and 3 ppm respectively. Conductivity of the water will not be a bar for pisciculture and irrigation. The dissolved CO₂ content is less during rainy season but in other seasons it is quite high. The total alkalinity is beyond the permissible limit during most of the months. During summer, dissolved solids content in the water of this jhor is very high and it is not suitable for irrigation purpose. The amount of suspended solid carried by this jhor has rendered the river water unfit for use during most of the period of the year.

Besides these physicochemical quantities, total soluble organic materials have been extracted from the water samples using chloroform and benzene successively; the amount of these substraces being 35–150, 85–500 and 200–600 mg dm⁻³ for the water samples of US, DS and EF respectively. These samples are under characterisation. After removal of organic components the water was digested with concentrated HNO₃ and concentrated HCl successively and analysed for metal ions. Fe, Mn, Zn and Cr have been detected in the sample collected from all the three stations. Besides these metals, Al, Ca and Na are also present in the samples of EF and DS.

Conclusion : It is evident from the physicochemical data that the upstream water at Talcher of the river Brahmani is suitable for use except the parameters BOD and COD. But the Nandira jhor delivers a heavy pollution load to the river and a large part of which gets deposited in the river bed during dry seasons. It becomes a constant source of pollutants for the downstream of the river at Kamalanga and Mangalpur. The conventional methods of water treatment will fail to remove organic matters and other toxic metals and as a result these will find their ways into the domestic water supply. The inhabitants of the villages situated on the bank of the river Brahmani of this zone are facing acute problem for water for their daily use as the river water is polluted. The downstream water is unsuitable for domestic use, for cattle feeding and even for irrigation also. The people of the said area are suffering from various

TABLE 2—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL DATA OF WATER SAMPLES OF THE NANDIRA JHOR JUST BEFORE MEETING THE RIVER BRAHMANI FROM MAY TO DECEMBER 1987

Parameters*	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
Temp. (°C)	31–32	31–32	31–32	29–32	28–30	28–29	25–26	25–26
pH	8.4–9.3	8.1–9.0	8.2–9.2	8.1–9.2	8.1–8.8	8.1–8.3	7.5–8.4	7.8–8.3
Dissolved O ₂	2.8–8.8	2.4–6.1	2.8–9.0	2.9–9.5	3.9–8.1	4.7–8.0	4.8–8.1	4.8–6.0
Conductivity (mmho cm ⁻¹)	0.27–1.4	0.24–0.88	0.17–0.77	0.24–0.81	0.24–0.77	0.54–0.75	0.25–2.4	0.4–0.46
Dissolved CO ₂	5.28–11.88	1.4–11.88	0.00–3.1	0.62–8.66	1.49–10.56	8.8–12.32	15.84–21.12	12.32–14.8
Total alkalinity	30–70	30–130	40–356	37–245	19–86	46–236	14–267	50–60
Dissolved solids	745–1920	712–4343	880–910	840–1405	1354–1358	1208–1332	1115–1186	1156–1173
Total solids (g dm ⁻³)	1.715–2.924	1.639–5.352	1.66–1.791	1.705–2.329	2.277–3.072	3.005–3.256	2.945–3.205	3.044–3.176
Total suspended solid	911–1029	793–1175	738–911	862–1029	912–1784	1614–2084	1827–2019	1871–2020

*Units in mg dm⁻³ wherever unit is not mentioned (except pH).

intestinal diseases, dysentery, jaundice and various skin diseases. Hence it is necessary to take precautionary measures to check the pollution of the river Brahmani.

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